

Transition Metal Complexes of Diacetyl Carbohydrazone Methyl Trimethyl Ammonium Chloride

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Diacetyl carbohydrazone methyl trimethyl ammonium chloride $[\text{CH}_3-\text{C}(=\text{O})-\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)=\text{N}-\text{NH}-\text{C}(=\text{O})-\text{CH}_2-\overset{+}{\text{N}}(\text{CH}_3)_3]\text{Cl}^-$ forms only (1:1) solid complexes with Cu^{II} , Co^{II} , Hg^{II} , Fe^{III} , Au^{III} , Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} . Ir and nmr spectra indicate that the ligand coordinates with the metals in keto form through the azomethine and carbonyl groups. Molar conductance, electronic spectra (DMF) and magnetic moments of the solid complexes explore their structures.

In continuation of our studies¹⁻⁶ on the useful complexes of hydrazones, viz. carbohydrazidomethyl-trimethylammonium chloride, the present work is concerned with metal complexes of diacetyl carbohydrazone methyl trimethyl ammonium chloride, $[\text{CH}_3-\text{C}(=\text{O})-\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)=\text{N}-\text{NH}-\text{C}(=\text{O})-\text{CH}_2-\overset{+}{\text{N}}(\text{CH}_3)_3]\text{Cl}^-$, abbreviated as (DGT)Cl. These hydrazone ligands coordinate as bidentates in keto or enol forms via C=N and C=O groups. The ir band of either groups when the ligand reacts in keto form, is unaffected on chelation^{5,7} or is shifted to higher frequency⁶ probably due to an increase in bond order⁸ when back-donation from the metal takes place.

Experimental

The ligand and metal complexes were prepared according to the general method described previously¹. Ir (nujol) and electronic spectra (DMF) of solid complexes were recorded on Unicam SP 2000 infracord and SP 1800 spectrophotometer, respectively. Conductance values of 10^{-3} M solutions in DMF at 25° were measured by a M.C.3 (England) type bridge. Nmr spectral measurements were carried out on a Varian instrument. Magnetic moments were determined by the Gouy method and corrected for diamagnetism of the component atoms using the Pascal's constants⁹. Molecular weights were determined by freezing point depression method.

Results and Discussion

The results of elemental analysis are listed in Table 1. It is evident that the stoichiometry of the isolated complexes could be formulated as $[\text{M}(\text{DGT})\text{X}_2]\text{Cl}$, where $\text{M} = \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$, Co^{II} , Hg^{II} , Cd^{II} and Zn^{II} and $\text{X} = \text{Cl}$ or Br , and Fe^{III} and Au^{III} complexes as $[\text{Fe}(\text{DGT})\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$ and $[\text{Au}(\text{DGT})\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$. All the complexes were partly soluble in common organic solvents, but fairly soluble in

DMF and DMSO. The ligand (DGT)Cl, $[\text{CH}_3-\text{C}(=\text{O})-\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)=\text{N}-\text{NH}-\text{C}(=\text{O})-\text{CH}_2-\overset{+}{\text{N}}(\text{CH}_3)_3]\text{Cl}^-$ is an 1:1 electrolyte in DMF with molar conductance, $\Lambda_m = 78 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ (Ref. 10) at 25°. The isolated complexes were 1:1 electrolytes. Aqueous solutions of these complexes gave immediate precipitate with sodium tetraphenylborate, which is known to yield precipitates with big cations¹¹. Decomposition of these precipitates with nitric acid and on subsequent treatment with silver nitrate yielded a precipitate of silver halide, indicating the presence of halide in the complex cations. Furthermore, the presence of chloride in the outer sphere of the complexes was qualitatively shown by ion-exchange experiments. When coloured solutions of the complexes were poured onto a column packed with a cation-exchange resin in the H-form, complex cations exchanged with the resin H^+ ions. The effluent solutions were colourless and gave white precipitate of AgCl when treated with silver nitrate.

The ir spectrum of the ligand exhibit a strong broad band in the region $1723-1680 \text{cm}^{-1}$ which accomodates both the ketonic group of the diacetyl and the amidic one of the ligand. The band at 1610cm^{-1} is attributed to the azomethine $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$. In the ir spectra of the complexes, $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ is shifted to lower frequency by $5-15 \text{cm}^{-1}$ whereas $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ was nearly unaffected on chelation or was raised by 10cm^{-1} probably due to an increase in bond order⁶ or to prevention of inter-molecular hydrogen bonding present in the ligand molecules between C=O and NH groups of the hydrazide residue which was not compensated for by the lowering in $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ as a result of coordination. However, in the spectra of Hg^{II} and Fe^{III} complexes, $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ shifted to lower frequency by 25cm^{-1} . The C=O group of diacetyl residue is a weak site of coordination compared to the C=O of hydrazide. The C=O group of carbohydrazido methyl trimethylammonium chloride is very active as a site of coordination because of its presence, besides an adjacent

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF LIGAND AND COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour/ nature	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			M.p. °C	Λ_m $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	Mol. wt. Found/(Calcd.)
		Cl	N	M			
$\text{C}_9\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}^*$	White fine needle	15.2 (15.1)	17.5 (17.8)	—	255	78	230.5 (235.5)
$[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}_2)\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	Faint brown powder	25.9 (26.2)	10.1 (10.3)	15.2 (15.6)	200	78	400.5 (405.9)
$[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{Br}_2)\text{Cl}]$	Brick red crystal	—	9.8 (9.15)	14.1 (13.8)	195	78	451.4 (458.8)
$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}_2)\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	Faint blue powder	27.7 (27.75)	10.7 (10.96)	15.8 (15.4)	270	76	390.5 (383.3)
$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{Br}_2)\text{Cl}]$	Faint blue powder	—	8.9 (9.25)	13.5 (12.97)	259	76	462.3 (454.2)
$[\text{Cd}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}_2)\text{Cl}]$	White powder	25.9 (25.4)	9.5 (10.0)	26.2 (26.8)	>280	75	415.0 (418.8)
$[\text{Cd}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{Br}_2)\text{Cl}]$	White powder	—	8.0 (8.3)	21.9 (22.1)	272	75	515.5 (507.7)
$[\text{Zn}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}_2)\text{Cl}]$	White powder	28.5 (28.6)	11.1 (11.3)	17.2 (17.6)	>280	75	364.5 (371.7)
$[\text{Zn}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{Br}_2)\text{Cl}]$	White powder	—	8.8 (9.1)	14.2 (14.2)	270	74	455.0 (460.6)
$[\text{Hg}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}_2)\text{Cl}]$	White crystal	21.2 (21.0)	8.0 (8.3)	—	260	70	510.0 (506.9)
$[\text{Fe}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}]$	Yellow crystal	31.8 (31.4)	9.1 (9.3)	12.3 (12.4)	240	82	425.7 (415.7)
$[\text{Au}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}_2)\text{Cl}]$	Brown crystal	26.1 (26.3)	7.9 (7.8)	—	230	80	535.0 (538.8)

* Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.), Found : C, 45.8 ; H, 7.5. Calcd : C, 45.9 ; H, 7.6%.

methylene and NH groups. Consequently, the ligand may function as a bidentate in keto form through the azomethine nitrogen and carbonyl oxygen which is in agreement with our previous work³⁻⁶. Moreover, the nmr spectra of the ligand in DMSO gave a signal at δ 105 due to the NH of hydrazide residue which was located more or less at the same position for the diamagnetic Cd^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes. This confirmed that enolisation does not occur from NH- to the adjacent C=O group during complexation despite the fact of its presence in the free ligand as indicated by the presence of a broad band at 3400 cm^{-1} due to an intermolecular hydrogen bonded OH stretching frequency¹². Such band disappeared completely in the spectra of all the isolated metal complexes which is in concordance with our results. On the basis of elemental analysis of the isolated solid complexes, ir and nmr spectra, conductivity measurements and molecular weight determinations, the structure of the monoligand complexes of Cd^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cu^{II} , Co^{II} and Hg^{II} may be represented by structure 1.

(1)

M = Cd^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cu^{II} , Co^{II} , Hg^{II} ; X = Cl or Br, Me = $-\text{CH}_3$

The magnetic moment values of 4.6–4.4 B.M. (Table 2) for $[\text{Co}(\text{DGT})\text{X}_2]\text{Cl}$ complexes agrees with the reported value¹¹ for high-spin tetrahedral arrangement. Furthermore, the electronic bands observed at 16182 and 14670 cm^{-1} are due to the transition from the $^4\text{A}_1$ ground state to the $^4\text{T}_1$ (P) state. The fine structure is caused by spin-orbit coupling both of which split the $^4\text{T}_1$ (P) states itself and allow the transitions to the neighbouring doublet states to gain some intensity. Such transition further supports the proposed tetrahedral arrangement^{11,13}. The magnetic moments of the Cu^{II} halide complexes (Table 2) support this square-planar structure. Moreover, the complex shows two broad bands at 13788 and 12575 cm^{-1} in an

TABLE 2—SPECTRAL AND MAGNETIC DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	μ_{eff} B.M.	Ligand field bands* (cm^{-1})
$[\text{Cu}(\text{DGT})\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$	1.72	13 785(12), 12 562(11)
$[\text{Cu}(\text{DGT})\text{Br}_2]\text{Cl}$	1.76	13 782(12), 12 558(11)
$[\text{Co}(\text{DGT})\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$	4.60	16 182(302), 14 182(501)
$[\text{Co}(\text{DGT})\text{Br}_2]\text{Cl}$	4.40	16 175(295), 14 171(500)
$[\text{Fe}(\text{DGT})\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{Cl}$	5.70	15 145(45)

* Molar extinction coefficient in parenthesis, $\epsilon = \text{mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^2 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

agreement with those reported earlier¹³. The octahedral structure (2) may also be suggested for $[\text{Fe}(\text{DGT})\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{Cl}$. The magnetic moment value (5.7 B.M.) for Fe^{III} shows a high-spin complex and the band observed at 15165 cm^{-1} gives evidence for this octahedral structure. The $[\text{Au}(\text{DGT})\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$ complexes could acquire a square pyramidal structure (3).

(2)

(3)

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